

Population Characteristics and It's Impact on Socio– Economic Development, Geopgraphical Analysis of Nadia District, West Bengal

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Abstract

Population itself is an important aspect. Characteristics of population involves distribution of population, growth of population, religious composition, Linguistic composition, age composition, sex ratio, standard of Living, density and economic structure.

These characteristics are useful to understand population Personality of the region. The study is related to the distribution of Population. Population composition involves the Age and Sex composition, Religious and Linguistic composition, Economic composition and occupational structure. Therefore, the present study aims at comprehensive understanding of population characteristics and their socio-temporal variations. Recent figures related to characteristics of population and its various Aspects become available through the demographic study.

Economic development of a region is influenced by attitudes of people and their expectations. Importance of geographical region changes as per the attitude and expectation of the people which in turn influences distribution of population. Rapid growth of Population is considered to be an important determinant of growth.

Keywords

Population, Demography, Society, Literature, Labour, Economic Development, Agriculture.

Introduction

The proposed study aims to highlight the major characteristics of population and the impact of its on socio-economic development of the Nadia district which is located in the state west Bengal extending between latitudes, 22°53' N and 24°11' N and longitude from 88°09 E to 88°48 E having recorded 5167600 population In 2011 which invite the attention of the researcher to study the various pattern and the distribution of population on the basis of growth, distribution, composition, occupation and other major and minor components of population. Hence, the concentrated the topic of the research is,

'To study the population characteristics and its impact on socio economic development of the Nadia district in the context of geography'.

The study of population never be viewed in isolation. Population and other physical, industrial, environmental and geographical etc. factors are interrelated. Therefore, it is necessary to find out the adaptation of population in selected area with its minute detail, recording the various geographical resources, the influence of varied physical, industrial factors. Above all, how the principles of population left its impact and remarkable stamp on the socio- economic development of the region. Population itself is an important aspect. Characteristics of population involves distribution of population, growth of population, religious composition, Linguistic composition, age composition, sex ratio, standard of Living, density and economic structure.

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Economic development of a region is influenced by attitudes of people and their expectations. Importance of geographical region Changes as per the attitude and expectation of the people which in turn influences distribution of population. Rapid growth of Population is considered to be an important determinant of growth. Since economic

growth is measured in terms of an increase in per Capita income. Therefore, growth of population is influenced by economic factors such as per capita income and standard of living. Economic progress and growth of population are closely related. Because economic progress is related to the natural resources and the population that exploits these resources. If enough population is not available then all the natural resources will not be fully exploited, and production will remain low to that extent. Population is therefore is a major factor contributing towards production.

Objective of study

The major objectives of the present study are to make a Comprehensive study of population characteristics of Nadia Districts.

1. To know the influence of physical factors on population Distribution in Nadia District.
2. To find distribution and growth of population in different Parts of the districts.
3. To find out composition of the population on the basis of age, Sex, religion, occupation and economic Status of the Nadia district.
4. To analyse the impact of resources, literacy, and sex Composition on population characteristics of Nadia District.
5. To understand the overall population characteristics and its impact on the socio-economic development of the district.

Review of Literature

Dr. Yusuf Khan (1983), in his research work entitled 'Western Maharashtra- A study of population Geography', mainly Focuses on the topics of distribution and growth of population, Density, Sex and Age composition, literacy and occupational Structure, marital status and regional composition, urbanization and population problems in respect to Maharashtra. In the topic of sexed age composition, he analysed spatial pattern in sex ratio, rural and urban sex ratio, age composition, temporal variation in age structure, rural-urban differentials in age structure. He also calculated the dependency ratio.

Rajendra kumar Sharma (2004), '*Demography and Population Problems*', this is revised and updated edition mainly Includes concept of demography, factors determining sex ratio, age structure, dependency ratio, marital status and educational attainment.

Kayastha S.L. (2007), '*Geography of Population*', the author revived this volume in four sections as-Environmental perception, Problems and policies. In section second- Population characteristics and problems. In the section third- Problems of Urban and Rural Development and Migration. In fourth, 'population impacts of development and disasters. He introduced the natural and human resources and correlated with tourism potential in India. He also discussed the general characteristics of population as, population growth, literacy and religion.

Robert Wood (1979), '*Population Analysis in Geography*'. The author in this book emphasized the topics of sources and quality of demographic data, fertility and mortality trends, migration and models of population structure. He differentiated the boundary lines separating demography and population geography. He has given basic demographic equation which calculates the statistics of population growth and projections of population.

Sawant S.B; Athawale A.S.(1994), '*Population Geography*'. The author has explained the main topics regarding population characteristics in short but pin pointing nature. The book throws slight on distribution and growth of population with explaining the nature and scope of population geography. The author also focuses on Fertility, Mortality, Literacy, Migration and Urbanization in detail. The topic 'Composition of population' assessing Age composition, Sex composition, Economic composition with world scenario. Especially age composition expressed with diagrammatic representation of age pyramids. These forms of pyramids are illustrated with the help of statistics of different worldwide countries like Japan, Sweden, U.K, Philippines, etc. The author also enlightens the topic of planning and projection of population.

Bhende Asha and Kanitkar Tara (2010), '*Principles of Population Studies*'. The book is written by pair of authors which mainly gives population change for the world and India from ancient time up to the present period. Author raises the questions, what are the changes taking place? Where and what kind of people found? These questions state that the study of population is concerned with size, structure, distribution and changes over a period of time. The book tried to throw light on growth and distribution world as well as Indian population. Even their structure, characteristics, mortality, fertility, migration and population policies. In the topic 'population growth and distribution in India', author has given more detailed Information on population change and its measurements.

Hans Raj (2010), 'population Studies'. Author has divided the content of book in to three major headings as- 'Principles of Demography', 'World population Studies', and 'Population Studies in India'. The topic "Principles of Demography", gives concept, nature and scope of Demography. Author has also elaborated the interdisciplinary nature of Demography and methods and sources of data collection regarding the census of India. He examined statistical figures of population growth, composition, fertility, mortality, migration etc. to the World and Indian level. He observed that growth rate of population in India is considerably neutralized. Author also attempted to introduce census of India. He assessed the methodology of data collection and how transition is made in this regard. He put forth some new concepts used in 1991 census as major worker, marginal worker, agricultural labour and other workers.

Chandna R.C. (2011), 'Geography of population'. The book reveals general introduction to the population geography and its approaches. It includes chapters on distribution, Density of population, Race, Religion, population change, Migration, Literacy, Urbanization and theories of population. Author examined multifaceted environmental problems caused by population growth. He assessed it under the heading of impacts of population growth on lithosphere, on atmosphere, on hydrosphere and miscellaneous impact.

Alka Gautam (2009), 'Advanced Geography of India'. The book covers the physical, demographic, economic, cultural and developmental features of India. The author mainly assessed the comprehensive topics of historical background, resources, settlements, economic activities, regional planning and development of the country. The topic 'population' contributes population Characteristics of India, as Growth, Distribution, Density, Sex ratio, Age composition, Literacy, Urbanization, Occupational structure, Linguistic composition, Religious composition, Migration and problems and policies.

Datt Ruddar and Sundharam K.M.P. (2006), 'Indian Economy'. The content of the book is elaborated in five parts. Part first gives analysis of structure of Indian economy. Part second relates with planning and economic development. Part entitled Agriculture in the national economy, the main sub-topic discussed here are, the productivity trends, and land use and crop pattern. Part fourth as an 'Indian industries' deals with industrial patterns. Part fifth relates with 'The tertiary sector in the Indian economy', mainly deals with problems of transport and communication.

Dr. Subarna Bandyopadhyay (2024), in his research work entitled 'Economic engagement by women-a study at rural-urban context in the perspective of literacy rate for Nadia District, West Bengal, India' has explained the main topics regarding issue of women empowerment in agro-based economy. Education as a major social parameter is considered under this study to inter-relate women's work participation issue in the light of educational status.

Methodology

The data collected and use for the period of 1971-81, 1981-91, 1991-2001, 2001-2011 comes both primary and secondary Sources. At present there are seventeen block in Nadia district, Karimpur-I, Karimpur-II, Tehatta-I, Tehatta-II, Kaliganj, Nakasipara, Chapra, Krishnaganj, Krishnanagar-I, Krishnanagar-II, Nabadwip, Santipur, Hanskhali, Ranaghat-I, Ranaghat-II Chakdaha, Harighata.

The study is concentrated only on population characteristics of Nadia district. The data for the present study were collected with the help of observation, informal in-depth interviews, key informant interviews, case studies and census schedules. The primary data is the raw data collected through different sources for which special questionnaires were designed and Information collected through various offices and peoples. Besides the above, Secondary data is also collected from the census handbook, District statistical abstract, Socio-economic Review of Nadia district, Statistics from government offices As, District statistical department and Gram panchayat offices. The data collected through primary and secondary sources were processed and presented by statistical and cartographic techniques. These involves Population growth rate, Decadal Growth Rate, Dependency Ratio, Sex Ratio, Work Participation Rate, Arithmetic Density, Age-sex specific rate and Crude Literacy Rate. The different techniques and methods such as Maps, Graphs, Calculation, and Isopleth, Choropleth and divided circle are used.

Location Map of Nadia District

Block Wise Distribution of Population In Nadia District

According to the 2001 census the total population of Nadia district is 4604827 having 36255308 rural populations and 979519 urban populations and according to the 2011 census the total population of Nadia district is 5167600 having 3728727 rural populations and 1438873 urban populations.

According to the census report of 2011 in among the 17 Block of the district are Chakdah Tehsil (405719) is the most populated and Nabadwip Tehsil (135314) the best other Tehsil. In order of their size of population are (1) Nakashipara (386569), (2) Ranaghat-II (364405), (3) Kaliganj (334881), (4) Krishnagar-I (314833), (5) Chupra (310652), (6) Hanskhali (293040), (7) Tehatta-I (244322), (8) Santipur (241080), (9) Haringhata (231068), (10) Karimpur-II (217136), (11) Ranaghat-I (215137), (12) Karimpur-I (183556), Tehatta-II (151231), Krishnaganj (146705), Krishnagar-II (139472).

Among the 10 town of the district areas of Krishnagar Municipality (153062) is the most populated and the least is Cooper's Camp (N.A.A) (23119). In order of their size of population other Urban areas are (1) Santipur (M) (151777), (2) Nabadwip (M) (125543), (3) Kalyani (M) (100575), (4) Chakdah (M) (95203), (5) Ranaghat (M) (75365), (6) Gayeshpur (M) (58998), (7) Taherpur (NA+OG) (38039), (8) Birnagar (M) (30799) as per the census of 2011 AD.

Table 1.1 Nadia District: Block Wise Population Distribution 2011

Sl.no	Cd block	Rural population			Urban population		
		Person	Male	Female	Person	Male	Female
1	Karimpur-I	160895	83014	77881	22661	11557	11104
2	Karimpur-II	217136	111488	105648			
3	Thehatta-I	244322	125875	118447			
4	Thehatta -II	151231	77299	73932			
5	Kaliganj	306197	157234	148963	28684	14678	14006
6	Nakashipara	352191	180990	171201	34378	17527	16851
7	Chapra	296529	152575	143594	14123	7161	6962
8	Krishnagaj	146705	75573	71132			
9	Krishnanagar-I	285885	147239	138646	153062	77146	75916
10	Krishnanagar-II	134032	68826	65206	5440	2788	2652
11	Nabadwip	76241	39515	36726	125543	65415	60128
12	Santipur	154256	79482	74774	151777	77011	74766
13	Haskhali	245889	127576	118323	47141	24069	23072
14	Ranaghat-I	120847	62661	58186	127058	64248	62810
15	Ranaghat-II	314519	16237	152282	73005	37048	35957
16	Chakdaha	314383	162899	151484	346112	175199	125957
17	Haringhata	207459	106629	100830	23609	12080	11529
TOTAL		3728727	192112	1807615	1438873	732656	706217

Source: Census of India 2001 & 2011

NADIA DISTRICT : POPULATION DISTRIBUTION

Table: 1.2 Block wise Persons Engaged in Agriculture of Nadia District for the year 2011-12

Sl.no	Name of block	Bargadars	Patta holders	Small farmers	Marginal farmers	Agricultural labourers
1	Karim pur-I	4538	4114	2448	10568	30844
2	Karimpur-II	6139	6241	5204	18446	40544
3	Thehatta-I	5122	10921	5795	22661	34935
4	Thehatta -II	2388	6067	5088	16651	20474
5	Kaliganj	6419	7183	7952	30726	49299
6	Nakashipara	6089	7687	4251	27581	58048
7	Chapra	6117	7843	7709	28033	47002
8	Krishnagaj	3000	4112	2770	13341	19844
9	Krishnanagar -I	4337	5728	3875	17756	38888
10	Krishnanagar -II	2670	3905	3916	16985	18764
11	Nabadwip	1700	6511	750	6597	8909
12	Santipur	3366	4876	3005	19302	21254
13	Haskhali	4937	5750	3913	20635	30222
14	Ranaghat-I	1844	5145	2238	16457	17805
15	Ranaghat-II	2895	6543	6148	31245	40018
16	Chakdaha	2119	6922	4418	20907	42654
17	Haringhata					

	Notes 1)	Marginal farmer possesses agricultural land measuring upto 1 hectare	
	2)	Small farmer possesses agricultural land measuring more than 1 hectare and upto 2 hectares	
	* According to Agricultural Census (W.B.), 2010-11		

Analysis

Population Density

The concept mainly related to the number of the peoples and land area is called the general density of population. Therefore, in studying population characteristics of a geographical area density of population is important element. It gives direct relation between the size of population and the geographical land area.

Thus, it is thus measurement of the incidence of population concentration and is generally expressed in terms of persons per square kilometre or per square miles of land area rather than of gross area (land and water).⁴² In short population density gives- the pressure of population over a land area, which can be measured in sq. km. or miles. Thus, it is a measurement of persons per sq. km. or per sq. miles of land area. In this arithmetic ratio calculation, numerator is population number and denominator are area. So, the general density is also known as 'Arithmetic Density'. It is calculated with the help of following equation.

$$\text{Density of population} = \frac{\text{Total population.}}{\text{Total Area.}}$$

Types Of Density: Various densities are concern with their utility in various types of analytical studies, so they are calculated as

Arithmetic Density: It is a ratio between total population and total area of the region. It is expressed in terms of persons per sq.km. or persons per sq. miles. It is useful in understanding the man-land relationship.

$$\text{Density of population} = \frac{\text{Total population.}}{\text{Total Area.}}$$

Physiological Or Nutritional Density: It is a ratio between total population and area under agriculture. It is expressed in terms of population per acre of area under

agriculture. It is quite useful for the countries whose economy is based on agriculture.

$$\text{Nutritional Density} = \frac{\text{Total population.}}{\text{Land under Agriculture.}}$$

Agricultural-Density: It is ratio between people engaged in agriculture and area under agriculture.

$$\frac{\text{Number of people engaged in Agriculture} \times \text{Agricultural Density}}{\text{Total area under Agriculture.}}$$

Therefore, the agricultural density is expressed in terms of agricultural population per unit of cultivated area. It has proved to be a useful index of man land relationship in primarily an agrarian context.

Critical Density: It is a measure of number of people that can be supported by a region with the present land-use system. It gives the maximum density of population that the region can support continuously without damaging land in the existing environment,

$$\text{Critical Density} = A/B \times C/D$$

Whereas A= Proportion of land under agriculture.

B= Proportion of unused land.

C= per person area under agriculture.

D= Area of the land that can be cultivated with traditional methods of agriculture.

Economic Density: It is ratio between total requirements of population of a region and total productivity of the region. It is obtained with the help of following equation.

$$\text{Economic Density} = NK/SH$$

P = Total population. - K = Requirements per person. .

Therefore NK = Total population X Requirements per person.

= Total requirements of the population of the Region.

S = Total Area.

IT = Productivity per sq.km.of area.

SIT = Total area X productivity per sq.km, of area.

= Total productivity.

When this ratio is one, then the balance between total requirements of the region and total productivity of the region is ideal.

When the ratio is less than one, it means productivity of the land is more than its total requirements.

When this; ratio is more than one, then it means the productivity of land is less than its total requirements.

“Geographers, by way of manipulating the numerator or denominator, have devised various types of densities having a varying degree of utility in different situations. The objective, of course, has been to arrive at a better -understanding of the population-resource relationship. These ratios have been called as Arithmetic density. Economic density etc”.⁴⁴ Out of these densities population density is very useful tool in the analysis of density of man’s distribution in the surrounding. ‘However (dark 1972, p-29) rightly observed that, the concept of density of population is most divulging and is a useful tool in the analysis of diversity of man’s distribution in space. Demko (1970 p-22) recognizes that the land and people constitute the few significant elements of an area and therefore, the ratio between the two is of fundamental interest to all scholars concerned with population analysis.

NADIA DISTRICT : POPULATION DENSITY (2001 - 2011)

Table 1.3 Percentage of Literacy by sex in rural and urban areas in the district of Nadia, 2011

Sub-Division / C.D.Block / M / N.A.	Rural			Urban			Total		
	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)
Tehatta Sub-Div.	69.04	64.42	66.80	84.00	80.34	82.20	69.47	64.89	67.25
Karimpur-I	67.81	63.27	65.61	84.00	80.34	82.20	69.82	65.44	67.70
Karimpur-II	63.35	60.65	62.04	-	-	-	63.35	60.65	62.04
Tehatta-I	73.68	67.56	70.72	-	-	-	73.68	67.56	70.72
Tehatta-II	70.93	65.99	68.52	-	-	-	70.93	65.99	68.52
Krishnanagar Sub-Div.	70.76	62.98	66.99	88.20	81.35	84.85	74.68	67.17	71.03
Kaliganj	67.96	62.08	65.10	80.22	72.72	76.56	69.04	63.02	66.11
Nakashipara	66.55	58.62	62.70	89.62	81.96	85.86	68.68	60.82	64.86
Chapra	69.72	65.62	67.73	82.48	76.44	79.50	70.30	66.13	68.28
Krishnaganj	77.43	67.98	72.86	-	-	-	77.43	67.98	72.86
Krishnanagar-I	76.39	66.03	71.38	77.60	66.57	72.23	76.50	66.08	71.45
Krishnanagar(M)	-	-	-	92.59	88.11	90.36	92.59	88.11	90.36
Krishnanagar-II	72.28	63.32	67.93	87.30	77.93	82.70	72.88	63.92	68.52
Nabadwip	67.78	54.10	61.20	81.41	70.04	75.85	73.80	61.26	67.72
Nabadwip(M)	-	-	-	90.44	83.94	87.33	90.44	83.94	87.33
Ranaghat Sub- Div.	81.13	71.26	76.36	87.70	79.82	83.83	83.86	74.90	79.51
Santipur	75.02	63.71	69.55	83.80	74.43	79.27	78.23	67.63	73.10
Santipur(M)	-	-	-	84.94	76.73	80.90	84.94	76.73	80.90
Hanskhali	83.67	73.36	78.72	91.40	82.88	87.23	84.92	74.94	80.11
Ranaghat-I	79.18	69.98	74.76	85.26	75.96	80.70	82.08	72.89	77.61
Ranaghat(M)	-	-	-	95.04	91.33	93.19	95.04	91.33	93.19
Birnagar(M)	-	-	-	88.26	80.82	84.60	88.26	80.82	84.60
Taherpur(N.A.)	-	-	-	95.72	90.40	93.10	95.72	90.40	93.10
Ranaghat-II	82.83	73.76	78.44	88.51	80.98	84.80	83.66	74.85	79.38
Cooper's camp(N.A.)	-	-	-	91.30	79.72	85.61	91.30	79.72	85.61
Kalyani Sub-Div.	84.87	73.86	79.55	92.16	84.93	88.60	87.89	78.56	83.35
Chakdaha	83.81	72.40	78.32	89.72	81.81	85.85	85.14	74.57	80.03
Chakdaha(M)	-	-	-	93.61	87.93	90.80	93.61	87.93	90.80
Kalyani(M)	-	-	-	91.73	84.01	87.90	91.73	84.01	87.90
Gayeshpur(M)	-	-	-	94.19	86.71	90.49	94.19	86.71	90.49
Haringhata	86.48	76.06	81.42	92.60	84.14	88.47	87.11	76.90	82.15
District Total	74.76	66.69	70.85	88.95	81.63	85.35	78.75	70.98	74.97

N.B: Literacy relates to population aged 7 years and above
Source: Census of India, 2011.

Economic Composition

An important aspect of the study of population characteristics of the region is economic Composition of population. Economic status influence directly or indirectly several aspects of population, like standard of living which includes wage levels, purchasing capacity together collectively influence the standard of living of the people. Various criteria are used for the determination of economic activities of people. Such as economically active and non-active population, type of occupation, their importance and number of people engaged in them.

Economically Active and Non-Active Population

The Percentage or Proportion of Economically Active Population of a geographical area to the total population gives crude — efficiency rate for the region. To calculate dependency ratio for the region in this situation is also essential. Dependency ratio is nothing but a dependency burden of the population.

Dependency Ratio/ Burden

It is a ratio between economically non-active population of people below 15 years of age and those above 60 years and economically active population of those in the age group of 15-59 years.

Workers And Non-Workers Population

The phenomena of economically active Non-activeness of the population mainly deal with Number of people engaged in economic production. Proportion of economically active population to total population gives 'Crude efficiency rate' for the region.

Economically the study area is occupying a significant position in the State. Total agricultural land of the district is 390.66 thousand hectares. Almost 80% of the

land is used for agricultural purposes in the district where only 0.31% of the land is forest area. Production of crops like paddy, wheat, jute and vegetables are the main source of income in the district. Production of tally and bricks by the clay of the river bed are one of the main businesses here. The total numbers of brickfields are 274 in the district. Among them, 149 falls in Krishnanagar Sadar & Tehatta Subdivision, 59 under the Ranaghat subdivision and 66 are under the Kalyani Subdivision. Except for the sand and clay of the river, no any valuable minerals are available here.

Nadia district falls under the Hoogly industrial zone. At later part, a mini industrial area was also established in Kalyani. Spinning meal, bottling plant of I.O.C., Oxygen gas factory, herbal medicine factory of Dabur, Coalmark of Gayeshpur, Haringhata Dairy are the large and medium scale factories of Kalyani industrial belt. Except that Supreme paper mill of Chakdah and Chilling plant of Krishnanagar also play an important role in producing job opportunities in the district. Food processing industries, soft drinks and tobacco factories, cotton industry, leather industry, rubber, plastic and chemical industry, and production of non-metallic things are the main small-scale industry of the study area. Clay pot arts of rural area, bamboo-based industry, candlelight production and the Khadi are village-based industry of Nadia. Clay doll of Krishnanagar, embroidery, Terracota are the famous handmade art of the district. Shantipur, Nabwadip, Ranaghat-I, Kaliganj, Nakashipara, Tehatta blocks are famous for Baluchori, Jamdani, Tangail, Kanthastretch and other types of handloom saris. The total number of banks in Nadia is 185 and population per bank is 24 thousand where the number of primary agricultural banks is 561.

Production Of Principal Crops

Productions of crops are directly related to the agrarian economy. More production means more income for people related to agriculture. But hazards directly hamper the production of crops. So, the relation of crop productivity with hazards should be essential for analysing the actual condition of agrarian economy.

Table 1.4 Nadia District: Production Of Principal Crops

Crops	2009-10	2010-11	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14
Total Cereals	768.5	755.7	875.2	814.4	891.7
Total Pulses	32.4	44.6	49.3	53.4	51.2
Total Oilseeds	104.5	108.3	104.9	152.3	141.5
Total Fibres*	2049.7	1566.1	1763.9	1775.9	2090.9
Total Miscellaneous crops	252.2	262.1	417.8	371.8	358.3

Unit: Thousandtonnes.

*In 1000 bales of 180 kgs each (b) Less than 50 tonne
Sources: 1) Directorate of Agriculture, Govt. of W.B.
2) B.A.E. & S., Govt. of W.B.

In 2009-10 production of total crops was 768.5 thousand tonnes where it was 755.7 thousand tonnes in 2010-11 and it decreased 12.8 thousand tonnes than previous. Production of total pulses increased by 12.2 thousand tonnes, total oilseeds increased 3.8 thousand tonnes, and total miscellaneous crops increased by 9.9 thousand tonnes. But the production of total fibres decreased 483.6 thousand tonnes. That means the production of main crops like paddy, corn and just decreased in 2010-11.

In 2011-12 the production of cereal crops was 875.2 thousand tonnes and it increased 119.5 thousand tonnes than 2010-11. Productions of Pulses increased in 4.7 thousand tonnes but productions of total oilseeds decreased are 3.4 thousand tonnes in 2011-12 than 2010-11 respectively. Productions of total fibres were 1763.9 thousand tonnes and miscellaneous crops were 417.8 thousand tonnes respectively. That means both increased 197.8 thousand tonnes and 155.7 thousand tonnes in 2011-12 than the previous financial year.

Productions of cereal crops decreases 60.8 thousand tonnes, productions of pulses was increased little these are 4.1 thousand tonnes, productions of oilseeds was increased lot these are 47.4 thousand tonnes, productions of fibres was increased very little these are 12.0 thousand tonnes and productions of miscellaneous crops like sugarcane, potato, tobacco, tea, chillies, ginger and others decreases slightly these was 46.0 thousand tonnes respectively comparison to 2011-12 in 2012-13 financial years. Actually, the productions of cereal crops decrease in 2012-13 due to the flood of 2013 in Nabadwip, Shantipur, Ranaghat and Chakdah are proved partially by this scenario.

In 2013-14 productions of cereal crops increased 77.3 thousand tonnes, productions of pulses was decreased little these were 2.2 thousand tonnes, productions of oilseeds was decreased lot these were 10.8 thousand tonnes, productions of fibres like jute, mesta and cotton are increased very much these were 315.0 thousand tonnes and productions of miscellaneous crops like sugarcane, potato, tobacco, tea, chillies, ginger and others decreased slightly these were 13.5 thousand tonnes respectively comparison to 2012-13 financial years. Actually, the productions of cereal crops decreased in 2012-13 due to the flood of 2013 are proved partially by this scenario. Most of the areas under the district of Nadia are free from floods in 2014 and for this reason, the production of cereals and fibre increased very much in this year. But some hazards happen in the latter part of 2014 and the first part of 2015 especially Chakdah, Ranaghat, Haringhata in winter season which was the reason of slight decreased in the productions of oil seeds, potato, ginger etc.

Conclusion

Economic Composition of population is an important aspect of the study of population characteristics of the region. 'Human beings not only considered as merely source of biological reproduction but source of knowledge, because knowledge cannot be confined to the four walls of any nation. In other warder, reduction which cost of one invention brings, can be calculated by applying standard to the workers spread all over the world.' Economic status influence directly or indirectly several aspects of population, like standard of living which includes wage levels, purchasing capacity together collectively influence the standard of living of the people. Various criteria are used for the

determination of economic activities of people. Such as economically active and non-active population, type of occupation, their importance and number of people engaged in them. 'Population of an area positively definitively effects its economic growth. It is because manpower provider human labour essentially needed for economic development and growth'.

'The manpower consists of only those persons who could participate in economically gainful activities in the event of need. In other words, manpower of the nation consists of those persons who are fit enough to produce goods and services and who have the propensity to participate in the economically gainful activities. Different countries classify manpower further into two subcategories of economically active population and economically non-active population. The economically active population is that part of manpower, which is actually engaged in the production of goods and services. It consists of both males and females. Economically non-active population is that part of manpower, which is engaged in activities like household duties in their own house or at the place of their relatives, retired personnel, inmates of institutions, students and those living on royalties, rents. Dividends, pensions etc.'. 'It is obvious that the very young, very old, as well as physically and Mentally incapacitated persons are not useful for economic activity. It is therefore, accepted that only those who can produce goods and service constitute the manpower of any nation. The economically active population is that part of manpower which actually takes part or tries to take part in the production of goods and services.

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